

Opinion:

Geopolitical Context of the Embattled Climate Racket

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SUMMARY

Several global generic ideologies were seeded by the USA-controlled United Nations (UN) of the early 1990s, following the dissolution of the USSR, and were actively percolated into all Western institutions (education, propaganda instruments, law, governance, hiring policies, etc.) (Rancourt, 2019). These delivered generic ideologies became tied to and protected by strong career and institutional interests, but also spun towards absurd and damaging lucrative endpoints (e.g., gender equity replaced women's rights and morphed into the gender fluidity that feeds a grotesque medical industry). The thus introduced and evolving ideology of climate change is an ideology centered on a fictitious kind of climate change that is mitigated by good behaviour, large investments using public funds, and industrial restructuring. It is a protection racket with no valid scientific justification. I describe the geopolitical, Western global elite, Big Finance and Big Tech contexts that have recently led to a USA Trump administration withdrawal from the climate imperative. The withdrawal is seen in the administration's abandonment of the relevant 1992 UN treaty, in the Department of War cleansing itself of "climate change crap", and in Bill Gates' recent public distancing from the climate apocalypse.

Definition of a protection racket

“A protection racket is a criminal scheme where a group extorts money (called “protection money”) from individuals or businesses by threatening them with violence, damage, or disruption, while simultaneously offering to “protect” them from those same threats, often created or exaggerated by the racketeers themselves. It’s essentially extortion disguised as security ...” —Google AI

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▶ The climate change imperative is an imposed ideology for globalist elite control and exploitation

The ideologies of climate change, gender fluidity and language toxicity censorship are not diseases that arose spontaneously or from science. Rather, they were systematically introduced top-down using United Nations (UN) sponsored machinations in the early 1990s following the dissolution of the Soviet Union and are engineered and maintained instruments to facilitate structured global elite predation of the Western captured world. I showed this in my 2019 essay entitled *“Geo-Economics and Geo-Politics Drive Successive Eras of Predatory Globalization and Social Engineering—Historical Emergence of Climate Change, Gender Equity, and Anti-Racism as State Doctrines”* ([Rancourt, 2019](#)).

Recently the Trump administration has—in the flailing and consolidating USA empire—withdrawn from the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) established in 1992 (*“Withdrawing the United States from International Organizations, Conventions, and Treaties that Are Contrary to the Interests of the United States”*, [The White House, 7 January 2026](#)).

This signals an internal battle between nationalist interests in the USA and Western globalist bankers previously more subservient to the USA. One of many signs of these tensions is the shocking *“Statement from Federal Reserve Chair Jerome H. Powell”* ([Federal Reserve, 2026](#)).

Basically, since the end of World War II and especially since the early 1990s dissolution of the USSR, dominant forces wanted control and compliance. During stable periods the best large-scale

compliance systems are ideological principles that are culturally integrated. Historically, these are cultural identity and religion. The applied religion or ideology benefits its managers and enables top-tier extraction of public wealth without revolt. (See the subsection “Mass-cooperation induced by organized religion” in [Rancourt, 2019](#), at pages 35-37).

The modern Western globalists want weak national states and minimal social and family cohesion. Large nuclear and extended families are resilient ecosystems that can be refractory against external manipulation (Todd, 2024), so they are dismantled and disincentivized. Similarly for independent thought and business, and private property, so they are disallowed and regulated by institutions and laws. An overarching theoretical frame is presented in my “Conceptual Model of State Collapse” ([Rancourt, 2026](#)).

Independent competing traditional ideologies are ridiculed and neutralized—and also instrumentalized against threatening social classes—using employer discipline, a co-opted educational system and powerful constant propaganda. The resulting atomized and indoctrinated individuals are given identities and shared values using delivered generic ideologies, including the ideology of climate change, which is an ideology centered on a fictitious kind of climate change that is mitigated by good behaviour, large investments of public funds, and industrial restructuring.

The ideological frames that were seeded and nurtured by the largely Western and Western-elite-captured UN and that were percolated to all Western institutions (education, military, etc.) create the conditions for optimized global predation (Rancourt, 2019). Nations and their citizens—under so-called democracy with elite-chosen fake so-called representatives—even came to promote “attracting investment” as the preferred means of development, thus begging to be exploited; while elite players, who are often lead cheerleaders of the global generic ideologies, rake in billions from stock market transactions and large public investments.

The thereby enabled structural funnelling of wealth from occupied and captured nations and from the lower and middle classes to the Western globalist elite is socio-historically referred to as “the wealth pump”. It is recognized to cause continental-scale harm and suffering (Centre for Applied Research, Norwegian School of Economics et al., 2015; Fernandez and Hendrikse, 2020), accompanied by intense actual environmental degradation. And, it spontaneously evolves towards excess that becomes destabilizing to the point of causing large-scale meltdowns and failures or “resets” (Fischer, 1996; Todd, 2024; Turchin, 2023).

Basically, the climate change imperative, [like military arms sales and the COVID-19 mRNA vaccines](#), is a protection racket in which the state extorts public funds to protect the public from a fictitious global calamity described by the state. We can add global infant so-called immunization campaigns ([Rancourt, 2025](#)).

This is the framework for understanding climate politics.

► Utilitarian purposes of the delivered end-of-history ideologies

In-effect the main purpose of the post-USSR Western generic ideologies of climate change, gender fluidity and language toxicity censorship was to facilitate political manipulation and exploitation of the thus groomed occupied public and enable lucrative universal care and protection rackets.

Also, rapid organic population growth itself and large populations in themselves are threats to protected societies of elites living in gated domains because of unpredictability and difficulty to surveil and control, and because large new populations spawn new and powerful elite competitors. The imposed climate change ideology offers both the promise of a lever to slow or prevent growth via emission control and an ideological pretext for complete surveillance and control of movement and consumption (30-minute cities, digital money).

There is also the ever-present and often dominant geopolitical dimension. The new ideologies can be used to justify war (to save women, to bring democracy), or simply to vilify geopolitical opponents (because they supposedly pollute, have large populations, reject gender fluidity, have their own state religions, and so on).

In addition, climate narratives are used to cover up large-scale human and environmental disasters caused by global finance demands and investment and trading scams, and climate dogma is reinforced by blaming local disasters and mismanagement on climate change. One common example is dismantling or incapacitating water management facilities supposedly in the goal of environmental restoration and then blaming resulting floods on climate change. This is not unlike declaring and “responding” to a [fake pandemic](#) as a cover for targeted bio-weapon, physical, psychological or chemical attacks, and falsely blaming local health events or artificial testing anomalies on circulating pandemic-potential viruses and their presumed variants. For the pandemic context see “*Constraints from Geotemporal Evolution of All-Cause Mortality on the Hypothesis of Disease Spread During COVID*” by Hickey et al. ([2025](#)).

Finally, geopolitics is relevant in contracting or expanding the global territory of Western finance occupation and industrial wealth extraction. Part of the pressure favouring Western expansion is from media propaganda and institutional capture that penetrate competing geopolitical blocs (Russia, China, BRICS) and promote the global ideologies of climate change, gender equity, and plutocracy as the highest form of democracy—all presented as opposing bad and promoting good—while displacing established societal networks.

In addition, there is widespread CIA-sponsored terrorism and interference, where a more direct approach is practical.

► Western elite infighting over ideological instruments

Contrary to the wishful thinking of many, any vulnerability of climate change ideology does not arise from the palpable nonsense of scientific propaganda about tipping points, rising sea levels, scorched earth scenarios, climate migration, species extinction, environmental collapse, and increasing

frequency and magnitudes of extreme weather events. Propaganda, institutionalized education and career interests have easily captured the professional and managerial classes (including scientists) on all these points. Whereas all severe environmental degradation is actually due to large-scale oppression and industrial practices ([Rancourt, 2007](#)).

As with any dominant system or instrument of elite parasitic exploitation on a territory, the main factor determining the dynamics of climate ideological oppression and the dynamics of implementation of climate instruments of control and wealth extraction is the constant battle between opposing elite factions. Logic and actual and independent science have relatively little impact.

Any system of dominance always attracts and must repel elite challengers (Turchin, 2023). The elite factions or blocs in the USA are no exception. Popular sentiment or protest are largely irrelevant most of the time.

The said constant battle of varying focus and intensity between competing elite factions concerns both conflicts about the overall strategy benefiting all the major elites and conflicts over control of domains of wealth extraction. A good example is tying individual resources to national electronic control as an optimal national (or supranational) robust real-world basis for currency, which China has already largely achieved, whereas in the USA there is a limiting mega battle or turf war on the “how to” between Big Finance and Big Tech, as explained by Yanis Varoufakis ([Varoufakis, 2024](#)).

Climate change ideology is vulnerable to the said battles between competing elite factions in the USA, as corroborated by the above-mentioned USA Trump administration 7 January 2026 withdrawal from the UNFCCC. The vulnerability may arise from competition between the industrial base (including energy extraction and military industries) and globalist high finance interests, which are somewhat connected to the MAGA base and the captured professional classes, respectively.

Battles between competing elite factions in the USA, and realignment of priorities, therefore have produced a recent and surprising abandonment of climate priorities:

- Chief globalist representative of protection rackets Bill Gates publicly distanced himself from catastrophic survival-threatening climate scenarios, insisting instead that we must save the world through health initiatives (specifically, his publicly funded infant vaccination programs) ([Gates, 2025](#); [CNBC Television, 2025](#))
- The Trump administration of the USA has cleansed the “climate change crap” from the policies and concerns of the newly named Department of War ([Hegseth, 2025](#); [Waldman, 2025](#))
- The USA is withdrawing from the UNFCCC (The White House, 2026)

Now those are tipping points.

The said battles between competing elite factions in the USA are themselves not determined but driven by geopolitical and geoeconomic forces in the rapidly evolving world. Here, the competition between Asia (notably China, Russia, India) and the Western USA-captured world is fundamental. For example, maybe the climate change and vaccine preparedness programs are too expensive and

distracting in the face of planned and actual real hot wars and blockades (Ukraine, China, Venezuela, Iran)?

Maybe China is profiting more from the boosted green technological revolution? Maybe energy prices and movements risk being too confined by overarching carbon controls? Maybe the risk of rebellion over losing relatively inexpensive transportation options is too great? Maybe the energy industry sector has gained more leverage over Western global affairs, via the strategic and financial importance of oil and gas? Maybe the USA is considering and attempting a reinforced petrodollar currency comeback? Maybe geoscientists are finding it more and more difficult not to revolt against absurd claims? Maybe ordinary folks can no longer tolerate being blamed for weather? All these are potential factors.

► Existence or non-existence of a scientific basis is irrelevant

The difference between the climate and vaccine scams is that the vaccine industry has an intimate connection with defence projects whereas climate does not. Climate control is elusive and limited whereas the ability to con entire populations into pandemic fear and acceptance to literally be injected is demonstrated. The USA military purports to believe that the ability to protect against bio-threats by mass vaccination is a question of national security. A massive industry and supporting institutions are dedicated to and benefit and grow from vaccine preparedness. Military vaccine preparedness means that vaccines must continuously be produced at high cost (production facilities cannot viably be idle), which explains the flu and COVID-19 propaganda and imperatives. Chicken eggs are replaced by lipid nanoparticles for economic efficiency but the institutional and profit drivers remain.

Both scams (climate and flu or pandemic vaccines) are equally without any hard scientific basis, and both cause and contribute to immiseration of the lower societal strata.

All such scams are possible because the USA regime as an empire has been such a dominant power, not needing to be rational, efficient or fair in order to dominate, which is fertile ground for extreme elite corruption and over exploitation. As geopolitical constraints become more real, the USA through elite and popular struggles would need to somewhat abandon its ways and reform itself or follow in the path of all failed empires that imploded.

► There really is no scientific basis for the climate change imperative and there is no reliable measurable increase in global mean surface temperature

Finally, regarding the absence of science supporting climate change alarmism: Empirical evidence does not show increasing extreme weather. The basic planetary radiation balance physics shows insensitivity to increasing atmospheric CO₂. Atmospheric CO₂ is not determined by human activity. Sea levels are not measurably increasing, using reliable measures. The reported surface temperature data are contrived and in-effect fabricated, at best suffering from systemic confirmation bias.

I showed that the reports of increased forest fires are incorrect, in my 2016 article *“Anatomy of the false link between forest fires and anthropogenic CO2”* ([Rancourt, 2016](#)). I made a rigorous first-principles calculation of planetary radiation balance in my 2011 article *“Radiation physics constraints on global warming: CO2 increase has little effect”* ([Rancourt, 2011](#)).

Recently, Hickey showed based on access to information (ATI) documents and temperature time series data from the hundreds of Canadian weather stations that the claimed mean surface instrumental temperature trends for Canada are at best in error, in his extensive 2025 paper entitled *“Artificial stepwise increases in homogenized surface air temperature data invalidate published climate warming claims for Canada”* ([Hickey, 2025](#)).

► Tentative big picture overview

The geopolitical transformation that is the emergence of a multi-polar world and the loss of USA hegemony, coupled with intense elite USA infighting between Big Finance and Big Tech (Varoufakis, 2024), is causing the death of globalist generic ideologies seeded in the early 1990s (notably the climate change ideology) as the USA recalibrates and engages in hot wars of destruction (Ukraine, Iran, Lebanon, occupied Palestine, Yemen) and military territorial assertions (Venezuela, Cuba, Greenland).

The said globalist generic ideologies (climate change, gender equality which became gender fluidity, language anti-racism which engendered critical race theory) first served the empire and its parasitic elites by boosting both the USA dollar and predatory globalization while socially engineering a compliant public, but now hinder the empire as the said ideologies evolve towards ever more absurd endpoints. The empire presently seeks to increase efficiency and competence in vital sectors for hemispheric domination, while using war and covert operations to control the largest possible part of world resources, newly anchoring itself in AI governance and social engineering, and potentially an electronic currency (stablecoin).

The ideology-tied exploitation rackets most at risk immediately appear to be climate change and universal infant immunization, which extract huge rents from the Western public economy. Other presently pervasive scams will follow the same fate as the empire further recedes, as national sovereignties are recovered in many countries, and as the real economy of production and distribution becomes preeminent in most of the world.

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